

STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN CULTURE: MODERN DEMANDS AND APPROACHES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the development of the activities of leading personnel in the field of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with modern requirements, strategic leadership approaches and current issues of personnel policy.

Keywords: New Uzbekistan, people, leader, cultural policy, leadership spirituality, principle, third renaissance

Time does not rule you, you rule the time.

“We have every reason to say one truth with confidence. Uzbekistan is not yesterday's Uzbekistan - our people today are not yesterday's people,” our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized. History shows that people rule or are ruled. Only patient, resilient people overcome these life tests with fortitude. The weak always need someone to rule them. Also, our land of Uzbekistan has been ruled by different people for many centuries. In a word, it is true that our land has gone through many trials before it reached this level. Today, our society has taken on a unique appearance in every sphere. Let it be the sphere of culture, education, sports: in everything. The main reason for this is to establish and further develop the state of New Uzbekistan. Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said this about New Uzbekistan at a solemn ceremony dedicated to the 31st anniversary of our independence: “We all understand very well that building the New Uzbekistan that we are striving for today, creating the foundation of the Third Renaissance, is not an easy task. Such a grand task has many conditions and criteria. But the most important and decisive factor is the path of democratic reforms.”

Before we start talking about what a modern leader should be like in the development of New Uzbekistan, it would be appropriate to explain the word New Uzbekistan. This word, as defined by our President, means:

- a state that provides ample opportunities for every citizen to use public services in order to further improve their lives;
- a state where people can openly talk about their problems and work together to solve them;
- a state that provides unconditional justice for everyone and where citizens are equal before the law, regardless of their social status;
- a state where the necessary conditions are created for the development of entrepreneurship.

In a word, New Uzbekistan also means an open and fair society that cares for every citizen. So, what should leaders be like in New Uzbekistan? To answer this question, we must first understand who a leader is. The term leadership is used to refer to a person who knows the ropes of work, who gives his heart and soul to his profession, who works hard for himself, his family and the whole country, and who loves management activities with all his heart.

“Leadership requires high intelligence, a lot of energy, research and resourcefulness, constant work on oneself, and when the time comes, the necessary entrepreneurship. The following definitions can be given to the concept of leadership:

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1. A leader, as a social person, is a person who combines productive forces and production resources and acts as a manager of their main driving force.

2. To carry out any work, a leader first makes an independent decision. This decision determines the goal of the leader's entrepreneurial and business activities.

3. A leader is an entrepreneur who introduces new ideas, new initiatives, and new technologies into his field.

In addition, a leader should pay attention to the following:

1. The changing environment in which we live requires leaders to be able to effectively manage themselves and their time.

2. In connection with the erosion of traditional values, a modern leader is required to be able to demonstrate his personal values.

3. Since there is a huge opportunity to choose, the leader is required to clearly define both the goals of the work being performed and his own goals.

4. Continuously support their own growth and development through continuous learning.

5. Quick and effective problem solving is required.

6. Leaders must be agile and flexible in order to respond effectively to changing situations, that is, they must master strategic management techniques.

7. Due to the difficulties of traditional hierarchical relationships, effective management requires the use of the ability to influence people without resorting to direct orders.

8. Since many traditional management methods have exhausted their capabilities, new, modern management methods are required. It is necessary to master different approaches to their subordinates.

9. A leader must quickly create and improve teams that can be inventive and effective in their work. In addition, a leader must always be an example for his subordinates. That is why Albert Einstein did not say for nothing that "The best way to teach people something is to be an example for them," "The criterion for the activity of every leader is to make the dreams and hopes of the people his main goal and consistently realize them," said our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

In addition, the leading factors influencing the leader during his career are:

1. The need to know the language. For example, more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups live in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In our country, knowledge of foreign languages in the current era cannot fail to have its impact not only on leadership activities, but also on daily household services. In addition, knowledge of languages is an advantage for a leader. This is because the leader directly conducts cooperation with foreign countries, and in such a situation, the ability to speak a language is a useful aspect for a leader.

2. The issue of time. The most important problem for any leader today is the rational use of working time. Therefore, the initial stage of organizing managerial work on a scientific basis is to teach employees of the management system to use working time productively. As we have said above, time shortage is one of the problems that most worries leaders of all levels, because for them the time factor usually plays a decisive role. "Time is a resource that every leader has in equal quantities. Therefore, it is not important how much time he has, but how the leader uses the time he has effectively. "Time is such a rare resource," writes Professor K. Abdurakhmonov, "that it cannot be saved like money. It is the most inflexible element of our existence."

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3. The leader's ability to know modern technologies. We all know that the 21st century is the "century of advanced technologies," so leaders of our time must be able to use technology freely. This is certainly both a benefit and an advantage for the leader.

4. Leader's image. Image-(English - image, image) is a certain synthetic image that arises in the minds of people in relation to a particular person, organization and other social object, embodies information about the perceived object and encourages social behavior. In a word, the image of a leader is his appearance. Therefore, the style of dressing of a leader also has a great influence on his work. The most basic rule of the leader's image is that a person should not have more than 3 colors (this is the image of a leader or speaker, of course). Because if a person has more than 3 colors, the sphere of influence of a person decreases, the attention of the public is divided. Therefore, it is necessary to always observe dress etiquette.

5. The leader's speech etiquette. A study was conducted at the University of California, Los Angeles. What influences the public on a person speaking? Appearance is 55%, human emotions, that is, body movements are 38%, and what the speech is about is 7%. Of course, people have a very well-developed visual memory. It turns out that we get good information through vision. If we pay attention to what we are talking about, it is 7%. Especially since leaders appear in public, cooperate with other countries, cooperate with the heads of other organizations, and are constantly in communication with their subordinates, dressing and giving speeches in accordance with the image and speech rules helps to increase their sphere of influence and raise their respect.

At the same time, the responsibility of the leader is one of the main signs of the leader's culture, expressing his responsibility for a certain area. It differs from the responsibility of an individual in its breadth.

Thus, the responsibility of the leader has always been considered important. Responsibility is, first of all, the conscience of each person, as well as the collective's understanding of his duty to society and the nation. In general, responsibility is a sense of responsibility for the leader's task. All negative events in the leader's activities arise from a weak sense of responsibility.

The most negative manifestation of irresponsibility is political irresponsibility. Political irresponsibility causes the emergence of vices such as political short-sightedness, insincerity, deceit, fraud, etc. Therefore, a person in a leadership position requires a high level of consciousness, thinking, and alert perception. The main tasks that are set before the leadership cadres today, as well as the tasks that life requires, are as follows. A leader must be spiritually formed, with an open heart and a pure mind.

Leadership spirituality is the formed (internal) spiritual power of a leader. His spiritual and psychological culture is a set of emotional knowledge, valued at the level of values, based on the example of ancestors, which has reached the level of skills that regulate the spiritual world of a person. In order to improve his leadership potential, a leader needs to acquire knowledge that enriches his spiritual world, increase his ability to take initiative. The knowledge that has become the spiritual property of a leader will help him to limit his desires and protect himself from external pressures and influences. That is, being a spiritually competent leader involves the creative development of their valuable part. After all, any destructive idea can have its effect on a person who is poor in spirituality and does not have his own worldview.

The leader's knowledge of the secrets of the art of management, from selecting employees to finding rational solutions to conflict situations related to them, and the ability to mobilize the creative forces of the team to achieve high labor efficiency on the front for which he is responsible.

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Management is, first of all, working with people. A leader must have oratory skills, learn to speak in an understandable, expressive and impressive, convincing and inviting spirit. The leader's listening skills have become an urgent task today. Because the ability to listen inspires and motivates the speaker. Thus, new thoughts and ideas become possible. A leader must have a pure heart, an ambitious business leader, the ability to respond to negative or positive actions with the strength of the authority formed in him.

“Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader’s activity,” said our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Indeed, analysis develops a person, discipline leads to a goal, and personal responsibility forms the “I” in a person, which means that he needs to think through everything he does. It would be right to say that all of these are formed in a leader.

This Motherland, which is considered our sacred place where the umbilical cord blood of our ancestors was shed, has a handful of soil, clear water, clean air, colorful hills, and mountains that are so close to the heart that it is difficult to describe it in one word. Leading such a great Motherland, being responsible for its future generation, each community, devoting one's entire life to leadership work, and spending one's life for the prosperity of the country is a great happiness for every leader. We should be proud of such leaders. Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev is one of such leaders. Every word they say and the reforms they are implementing are a great lesson for young leaders. The proof of my words is confirmed in their following speech. “I want to say frankly: my nature absolutely cannot accept such a false life. Our people have placed their trust in me, and justifying this high trust, creating decent living conditions for our country - for me, the meaning of my life. Since I have taken responsibility for the fate of millions of people, it is absolutely impossible for me to take a different approach to reforms, to leave everything as it was.”

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